

Synthesis and antimicrobial screening of cyclohexenones and oxazines

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4-Cinnamoyloxybenzylidene (**1**) on condensation with various ketones yielded 1-aryl-3-(4'-cinnamoyloxyphenyl)-2-propene-1-ones (**2**), which on cyclization with ethyl acetoacetate in acetone and urea in alcoholic KOH furnished 6-carbethoxy-5-(4'-cinnamoyloxyphenyl)-3-aryl-1-cyclohexenones (**3a-h**) and 2-imino-4-aryl-6-(4'-cinnamoyloxyphenyl)-6H-2,3-dihydro-1,3-oxazines (**4a-h**), respectively. All the compounds were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Cyclohexenones and oxazines are associated with various pharmacological activities¹. In view of this, it appeared of interest to synthesize above derivatives bearing 4-cinnamoyloxybenzylidene moiety.

The starting compound 4-cinnamoyloxybenzylidene (**1**) was prepared by the reaction of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde with cinnamoyl chloride. The reaction of **1** with different aryl ketones yielded the corresponding 1-aryl-3-(4'-cinnamoyloxyphenyl)-2-propene-1-ones (**2**) which reacted with ethyl acetoacetate in acetone and urea in alcoholic KOH solution to furnish 6-carbethoxy-5-(4'-cinnamoyloxyphenyl)-3-aryl-2-cyclohexenones (**3a-h**) and 2-imino-4-aryl-6-(4'-cinnamoyloxyphenyl)-6H-2,3-dihydro-1,3-oxazines (**4a-h**), respectively.

Antimicrobial activity was determined by cup-plate dif-

fusion method². The zone of inhibition of the standards are as follows : amoxicillin, 20–25; ampicillin, 20–24; ciprofloxacin, 21–25; erythromycin, 20–25 mm, against bacterial strains and greseofulvin, 26 mm against *A. niger*. Compounds **3g** (20), **3h** (22), **4d** (20) and **4e** (22 mm) showed maximum activity against *E. coli*. Compounds **3a** (23), **3e** (25), **3h** (23) and **4f** (20 mm) were highly active against *P. vulgaris*. Compounds **3a** (22) and **4g** (22 mm) displayed maximum activity against *B. megaterium*. Compounds **3a** (20), **4a** (23), **4c** (20), **3h** (20), **4a** (22), **4e** (22), **4e** (21) and **4h** (24 mm) showed significant activity against *A. niger*. All other compounds were moderately active against the bacteria and fungus.

Experimental

All the m.ps. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR spectrometer, ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃ + TFA) on Bruker (300 MHz) and Hitachi 1200 (60 MHz) spectrometers using TMS as internal reference and mass spectra on a Jeol JMSD-300 spectrometer.

4-Cinnamoyloxybenzylidene (1) : A mixture of cinnamoyl chloride (1.6 g, 0.01 mol) and 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde (1.2 g, 0.01 mol) in dry pyridine (30 ml) was refluxed in an oil-bath for 1–2 h and set aside overnight. It was then poured in ice-bath, neutralized with conc. HCl and crystallized from ethanol, (2 g, 65%), m.p. 132°.

1-Aryl-3-(4'-cinnamoyloxyphenyl)-2-propene-1-ones (2) : A mixture of 4-cinnamoyloxy benzylidene (2.5 g, 0.01 mol) and acetophenone (1.34 ml, 0.01 mol) in methanol containing 40% NaOH solution (4–6 ml) was stirred for 24 h at room temperature. The mixture was then poured in icebath and neutralized with conc. HCl. The resulting solid was crystallized from ethanol, (2.6 g, 73%), m.p. 146° (Found :

C, 81.40; H, 5.38. $C_{25}H_{20}O_3$ requires : C, 81.52; H, 5.43%; $\nu_{\max}$ 3072 (C=CH), 1726 (COO), 1656 (C=O), 1573 (C=C), 1213 cm^{-1} (C-O-C); δ 6.78–7.98 (14H, m, ArH), m/z 46, 77, 91, 118, 163, 222, 253, 294, 388 (M^+). The other members of **2** were similarly derived from **1**.

3-Aryl-6-carbethoxy-5-(4'-cinnamoyloxyphenyl)-2-cyclohexenones (3a-h). A mixture of 1-(*p*-methylphenyl)-3-(4'-cinnamoyloxyphenyl)-2-propen-1-one (3.6 g, 0.01 mol), ethyl acetoacetate (1.3 ml, 0.01 mol) and K_2CO_3 (2–3 g) in dry acetone (20–30 ml) was stirred till acetone completely volatilized. The contents were then poured onto crushed ice and neutralized with conc. HCl. The resulting solid was crystallized from dioxane to give **3f** (2.56 g, 65%), m.p. 146° (Found : C, 77.45; H, 5.79. $C_{31}H_{28}O_5$ requires : C, 77.5; H, 5.83%; $\nu_{\max}$ 3050 (C=CH), 1733 (COO), 1690 (C=O), 1589 (C=C), 1205 cm^{-1} (C-O-C); δ 2.30 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 2.45 (3H, s, Ar- CH_3), 3.60 (2H, d, CH_2), 4.60 (1H, t, CH), 5.40 (2H, q, CH_2CH_3), 7.4–9.6 (13H, m, ArH); m/z 107, 120, 165, 196, 215, 242, 273, 307, 350, 371, 401, 428, 447, 466, 480 (M^+). The other members of **3** were similarly derived from **2** : **3a**, m.p. 151°; **b**, 153; **c**, 134°; **d**, 148°; **e**, 146°; **g**, 140°; **h**, 135°.

2-Imino-4-aryl-6-(4'-cinnamoyloxyphenyl)-6H-2,3-dihydro-1,3-oxazines (4a-h). A mixture of 1-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-3-(4'-cinnamoyloxyphenyl)-2-propen-1-one (3.8 g, 0.01 mol) and urea (0.60 g, 0.01 mol) in alcoholic KOH solution (15 ml) was refluxed for 10–12 h. It was then poured on to crushed ice, neutralized, and the resulting solid crystallized from ethanol to get **4e** (2.2 g, 51%), m.p. 140° (Found : C, 73.19; H, 5.10; N, 6.51. $C_{26}H_{22}O_4N_2$ requires : C, 73.23; H, 5.16; N, 6.57%; $\nu_{\max}$ 3375 (NH), 3030 (C=CH), 1699 (COO), 1548 (C=N), 1253 cm^{-1} (C-O-C); δ 3.89 (3H, s, Ar- OCH_3), 6.86–8.04 (13H, m, ArH), 8.15 (1H, s, C-NH), 8.17 (1H, s, =NH); m/z 51, 57, 91, 105, 122, 159, 230, 266, 301, 342, 370, 401, 426 (M^+). Similarly, other members of **4** were prepared from **2** : **4a**, m.p. 175°; **b**, 136°; **c**, 110°; **d**, 90°; **f**, 162; **g**, 143°; **h**, 168°.

References

1. B. H. Braff, B. H. Jane, C. M. Stuart and C. N. Roy, *Chem. Abstr.*, 2000, **132**, 12259; T. Kenji and S. Takashi, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1999, **130**, 38384.
2. A. L. Barry, "The Antimicrobial Susceptibility Test Principle and Practice," Illus Lea and Febiger, Philadelphia, 1976.